

FORMULATION OF CALAMANSI (*Microcarpa*) SOAP ENHANCED WITH BLUE TERNATE FLOWER (*Clitoria ternatea*)

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the formulation and development of Calamansi (*Microcarpa*) Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) extracts, utilizing three different treatments. An experimental design was employed, complemented by descriptive methods to evaluate consumer satisfaction. The study involved sensory evaluation by 30 participants across various age groups, assessing key attributes such as hardness, cleansing, lathering, conditioning, fragrance, and color. Results indicated that Treatment 1 was highly acceptable, particularly among teenagers, and demonstrated strong potential for commercial production. The soap was confirmed safe for use, showing no significant microbial presence, including *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. Based on these findings, recommendations were made to optimize product formulation, tailor marketing strategies, and conduct further research to enhance product appeal across different consumer segments. This research underscores the soap's market viability and highlights the importance of consumer-centered product development.

Keywords: *Calamansi Bath Soap, Blue Ternate Flower, Experimental Design, Consumer Satisfaction, Product Development*

INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for natural and eco-friendly personal care products has led to the exploration of novel ingredients and formulations in the cosmetic industry. This

research investigates the development of calamansi soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extracts, aiming to harness the potential benefits of these botanical ingredients in soap production. Soap is a vital personal care product, essential for cleansing and maintaining the skin's hydrolipidic film, which is crucial for moisturizing and protecting the skin (Draeos, 2012). Mild soaps, in particular, are beneficial for dry and sensitive skin, as they clean without stripping away natural oils, leaving the skin feeling refreshed and soothed (Ananthapadmanabhan et al., 2004).

Bath soaps, available in both bar and liquid forms, are indispensable household necessities used daily by consumers (Ildefonso, 2018). They not only cleanse but also help in managing skin problems and maintaining hygiene by eradicating germs (Hodgson, 2015). Traditional soaps, however, often have a high pH level of 9 to 10, which can disrupt the skin's natural pH of 4 to 5, potentially leading to issues like acne and dryness (Ehlers et al., 2001). Thus, there is a growing interest in soaps made from fruits and vegetables, which offer additional benefits such as vitamins and antioxidants that rejuvenate, whiten, and moisturize the skin (Brinkman et al., 2021).

Calamansi, scientifically known as *Citrus microcarpa*, is a small citrus fruit native to Southeast Asia, renowned for its high vitamin C content and antioxidant properties (Algas Alker, 2022; Cheong et al., 2012). Calamansi juice is believed to have various health benefits, including soothing acidity, promoting collagen production, aiding in weight loss, and improving skin health by offering an ascorbic acid burst necessary for tissue development and repair (Tammisetti, 2019). Its chemical composition includes citric acid, which imparts its sour flavor, essential oils that provide aromatic qualities, and flavonoids known for their antioxidant capabilities (Cheong et al., 2012). Additionally, calamansi contains polyphenols with anti-inflammatory properties and moderate levels of tannins, which contribute to its slightly bitter taste (Shahidi & Ambigaipalan, 2015).

The blue ternate flower, *Clitoria ternatea*, is a vibrant flower found in tropical regions, recognized for its rich anthocyanin content, which provides a deep blue hue and potent antioxidant properties (Jain et al., 2013). Traditionally used in Southeast Asian cuisine to color and flavor dishes, the blue ternate flower is also known for its medicinal applications, including diuretic, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant effects (Mukherjee et al., 2008). It contains bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, and triterpenoids, which contribute to its potential health benefits, including improved blood circulation, enhanced vision, and revitalized skin and hair (Dizon, 2014).

This study seeks to develop a "Blue-Mansi" bath soap, combining the beneficial properties of calamansi and blue ternate flower extracts. The abundance of calamansi in the Municipality of Aurora and its neighboring town of Cabatuan Isabela provides a sustainable source for this endeavor. The oversupply of calamansi often leads to wastage, making this initiative economically and environmentally viable (Bayani, 2020). Meanwhile, the blue ternate flower, though often overlooked, offers numerous health benefits and the potential for broader use in personal care products (Lim, 2016).

By incorporating these natural extracts into soap, the resulting product is anticipated to exhibit enhanced antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and skin-nourishing

properties. This study also aims to assess the feasibility of the developed soap through sensory evaluation by potential consumers and laboratory testing for its antimicrobial properties, conducted by a government regulatory agency. The innovative Blue-Mansi bath soap represents a competitive alternative to high-priced commercial soaps, offering natural skincare benefits suitable for personal, commercial, and industrial use (Kumar & Bhardwaj, 2018).

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extracts. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the processes involved in formulating Blue-Mansi bath soap in terms of the following treatments:
 - a. Treatment 1: Using 20 ml calamansi extract, 20 ml blue ternate flower, 59 grams of caustic soda, 150 ml water, and 330 ml coconut oil.
 - b. Treatment 2: Using 15 ml calamansi extract, 15 ml blue ternate flower, 59 grams of caustic soda, 150 ml water, and 330 ml coconut oil.
 - c. Treatment 3: Using 10 ml calamansi extract, 10 ml blue ternate flower, 59 grams of caustic soda, 150 ml water, and 330 ml coconut oil.
2. What is the degree of consumer acceptability of calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extracts in three treatments in terms of:
(a) hardness, (b) cleansing, (c) lathing, (d) conditioning, (e) fragrance, and (f) color?
3. Is there a significant difference in the general level of acceptability of the three treatments of calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extracts as perceived by the following group of respondents (a) teenagers, (b) adults, and (c) experts?
4. What is the antibacterial analysis of the calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extracts?

METHODOLOGY

Method of Research Used

The study used an experimental design. The experimental method is a systematic and scientific approach to research in which the researcher manipulates one or more variables, and controls and measures any change in other variables. Moreover, the descriptive method was also used since the respondents completed a survey questionnaire to find out the level of their satisfaction with the developed products.

Materials

The following tools, equipment, and ingredients shall be used during the conduct of the study. Preparatory tools, measuring tools, mixing tools, weighing tools, and curing tools and equipment are used during the conduct of the study as shown in the table below.

Table 1. Tools and equipment used in the development of calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extract

Description				
Preparatory Tools	Measuring Tools	Mixing Tools	Weighing Tools	Curing Tools
Pale	Measuring spoon	Wire whisk	Weighing scale	Curing Rack
Mixing Bowl	Measuring cup	Mixing bowls		Wax paper
Molder				
Hand gloves				

Ingredients

The table below shows the ingredients used in the making of Calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extracts.

Table 2. Ingredients used in developing blue-Mansi bath soap with three treatments

Ingredients	Measurement		
	Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
Caustic Soda	59 grams	59 grams	59 grams
Water	150 ml	150 ml	150 ml
Coconut Oil	330 ml	330 ml	330 ml
Calamansi Extract	20 ml	15 ml	10 ml
Blue Ternate Flower Extract	20 ml	15 ml	10 ml

Data Gathering Instruments

The instrument for data gathering was a score sheet using a quantitative analysis method to determine the acceptability of the products. The responses as to the level of acceptability of the calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extract in terms of *hardness, cleansing, lathing, conditioning, fragrance, and color* were determined with the use of a Five-point Likert scale as follows:

Table 3. Scale and Numerical Rating on the acceptability of the Blue-Mansi bath soap

Scale	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating
5	4.20 - 5.00	Highly Acceptable
4	3.40 – 4.19	Moderately Acceptable
3	2.60 – 3.39	Acceptable
2	1.80 – 2.59	Slightly Acceptable
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Acceptable

Data Gathering Procedure

In compliance with research ethics, the researcher prepared a letter addressed to the Teacher III and the Senior High School Focal Person of Cabatuan National High School, Isabelo L. Visaya Jr., Head to seek permission for the conduct of the study as well as to float the evaluation/score sheet particularly designed for the study.

Samples were brought to the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) RO2, Tuguegarao City for microbial analysis.

Upon approval, the Research Aide personally distributed the soaps accordingly. The RA systematically grouped them and visited them for skin effects weekly regarding the experiences/feedback of the respondents. Results were all recorded in the score sheets

From the accomplished score sheets, the scores were tallied, classified, organized, and presented in a tabular form to facilitate in-depth analysis and interpretation of data.

Sensory Evaluation

The finished products were subjected to sensory evaluation. Thirty (30) evaluators from various age groups were selected and properly oriented on what and how to evaluate the products using a score code. The samples were given to the chosen evaluators for evaluation purposes.

Consequently, the evaluators tried the samples from each treatment. Data on the *hardness, cleansing, lathering, conditioning, fragrance, and color* of each developed product were collected and coded for statistical analysis.

The evaluations and comments were recorded into a designed scorecard. Visitations were done weekly (Monday morning) to record the skin effects and it was done in three weeks. It was suggested that the soap be used daily to ensure fair and just evaluation.

Data Gathering Analysis and Statistical Tools Used

All data were gathered through questionnaires and evaluation forms were administered to the evaluators. The variables were analyzed and interpreted through the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Product Development

The soap-making procedure used by Ildefonso (2018) was adapted in the formulation of Blue-Mansi soap. Measurements of caustic soda and coconut oil were same in her study “Development of Calamansi-based Bath Soap” to produce 6 at 100 grams bar. Modifications were made to the weights to extracts as the researcher saw potentials of Blue Ternate flower in making bath soap. The procedure is listed below step by step.

Procedure

To create the soap, begin by dissolving 59 grams of caustic soda flakes in 147 grams of water, stirring continuously until the mixture is completely dissolved and has cooled. Next, add calamansi and blue ternate flower extract separately, continuing to stir the solution for 20 minutes. Once mixed, gradually incorporate 350ml of oil, ensuring to stir in a single direction for 45 minutes. After thorough mixing, pour the solution into molds and allow it to cool and harden for 24 hours. Following the solidification, remove the soap from the molds and let it age for 20 days to eliminate any potential irritation effects from the caustic soda. Once the aging process is complete, the soaps are ready for laboratory testing, distribution, and evaluation.

Through these stages of development, careful observation and analysis were done to come up with the Blue-Mansi Soap.

The following are the processes, procedures, and methods performed during the formulation of the product:

A. Lye Preparation

1. Measure Caustic Soda and Water
2. Dissolve Caustic Soda to Water
3. Leave Lye to cool within 24 hours

B. Blue Ternate Flower Preparation

1. Harvesting of fresh Blue Ternate Flowers in the morning

2. Wash thoroughly the Blue Ternate Flowers before extracting
3. Use a blender to extract the Blue Ternate Flowers

C. Calamansi Fruit Preparation

1. Harvesting Matured Calamansi
2. Wash thoroughly the harvested Matured Calamansi Fruit
3. Slicing the calamansi into halves.
4. Squeeze the calamansi fruit to extract, be sure to wash your hands before extracting.

D. Blue-Mansi Soap Preparation

1. Mix calamansi extract blue ternate flower extract and coconut oil in a mixing bowl.
2. Mix the solution for 5 minutes.
3. Pour the 206 grams of cooled lye then mix until dense or thickened, it could only be achieved by stirring continuously for 45 minutes.
4. When the mixture of blue-Mansi soap is already dense, pour it into the soap molder, then harden for 24 hours.
5. After 24 hours, remove it from the soap molder by unmolding it.
6. Cure for 20-30 days. The process will remove the irritation effects of caustic soda.

Consumer's Acceptability of Calamansi Bath Soap Enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts

Table 4. Degree of consumer's acceptability of calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extracts in three treatments (Treatment 1)

Respondents						
Evaluation Criteria	Teenagers	Description	Adult	Description	Expert	Description
Hardness	5.00	Highly Acceptable	4.70	Highly Acceptable	5.00	Highly Acceptable
Cleansing	5.00	Highly Acceptable	5.00	Highly Acceptable	4.60	Highly Acceptable
Lathing	4.90	Highly Acceptable	4.30	Moderately Acceptable	4.50	Highly Acceptable
Conditioning	5.00	Highly Acceptable	4.50	Highly Acceptable	4.70	Highly Acceptable
Fragrance	4.70	Highly Acceptable	3.90	Moderately Acceptable	4.00	Moderately Acceptable
Color	4.60	Highly Acceptable	4.60	Highly Acceptable	4.70	Highly Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.867	Highly Acceptable	4.5	Highly Acceptable	4.583	Highly Acceptable

As can be gleaned from the table, data suggests that the Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts in Treatment 1 was *highly acceptable* to the target consumer groups: teenagers, adults, and experts with an overall mean of 4.65.

In terms of hardness, the soap's hardness received an overall mean of 4.90 and was *highly acceptable* to all three groups, indicating that consumers find the soap's texture to be satisfactory.

With regard to cleansing, the soap's cleansing ability was *highly acceptable* to all three groups with a general mean of 4.87, implying that it effectively cleans the skin according to consumer expectations.

In the matter of lathering, while teenagers with a mean of 4.90 and experts with a mean of 4.50 found the lathering ability *highly acceptable*, adults rated it *moderately acceptable*. This suggests that the soap's lathering might be more preferred by younger users and experts, while adults have a slightly lower preference for this aspect.

As to conditioning, the soap's conditioning properties were *highly acceptable* to all three groups as shown by the overall mean of 4.73, indicating that it provides satisfactory moisturization and softness to the skin.

Regarding the fragrance, with a mean of 4.70, teenagers found the fragrance *highly acceptable*, while adults and experts rated it *moderately acceptable* with a mean of 4.5 and 4.583, respectively. This indicates that the scent of the soap may be more appealing to younger users compared to adults and experts.

In terms of color, with an overall mean of 4.63, the soap's color received *highly acceptable* ratings from all three groups, suggesting that consumers find the visual appearance of the soap appealing.

Overall, the Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts in Treatment 1 was well-received across various aspects by the target consumer groups. It demonstrates *high acceptability* in terms of hardness, cleansing, conditioning, color, and overall mean rating. However, there is a slight variation in preferences for lathering and fragrance among the different groups, with teenagers generally showing higher satisfaction in these areas compared to adults and experts. This information can be valuable for further product development and marketing strategies, considering the target audience's preferences and expectations.

Table 5. Degree of consumer's acceptability of calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extracts in three treatments (Treatment 2)

Respondents						
Evaluation Criteria	Teenagers	Description	Adult	Description	Expert	Description
Hardness	4.90	Highly Acceptable	4.30	Moderately Acceptable	4.80	Highly Acceptable
Cleansing	4.90	Highly Acceptable	4.50	Highly Acceptable	4.60	Highly Acceptable
Lathering	4.80	Highly Acceptable	3.90	Moderately Acceptable	4.30	Moderately Acceptable
Conditioning	5.00	Highly Acceptable	4.10	Moderately Acceptable	4.30	Moderately Acceptable
Fragrance	4.70	Highly Acceptable	3.80	Moderately Acceptable	4.20	Moderately Acceptable
Color	4.70	Highly Acceptable	4.00	Moderately Acceptable	4.30	Moderately Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.833	Highly Acceptable	4.1	Moderately Acceptable	4.17	Moderately Acceptable

As can be seen in the table, data for Treatment 2 suggests that the degree of consumer acceptability of Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts varies among different groups. With a general mean of 4.37, the product is *moderately*.

With regard to hardness, the soap's hardness was *highly acceptable* to teenagers and experts with a mean of 4.90 and 4.80, respectively. However, adults rated 4.30, thus, for them, it is *moderately acceptable*. This indicates that teenagers and experts find the soap's texture satisfactory, while adults have a slightly lower preference in terms of hardness.

As to cleansing, the soap's cleansing ability received *highly acceptable* ratings from all three groups as evidenced by a general mean of 4.67, suggesting that it effectively cleans the skin according to consumer expectations.

In terms of lathering, teenagers with a mean of 4.80 found the soap's lathering ability *highly acceptable*, while adults rated 3.90 and experts rated 4.30 showing that it is *moderately acceptable* for them. This implies that younger users and experts generally prefer the soap's lathering, while adults have a slightly lower preference in this aspect.

With reference to conditioning, the soap's conditioning properties were *highly acceptable* to teenagers as indicated by a mean of 5.00. However, having a mean of 4.10 and 4.30, respectively, adults and experts rated it *moderately acceptable*. This suggests that the soap provides satisfactory moisturization and softness to the skin according to teenagers and experts, but adults have a slightly lower preference in this regard.

Concerning fragrance, teenagers rated the soap's fragrance *highly acceptable* as shown by a mean of 4.70, while adults with a mean of 3.80, and experts with a mean of 4.20 rated it *moderately acceptable*. This indicates that the scent of the soap is more appealing to teenagers compared to adults and experts.

In respect to color, the soap's color received *highly acceptable* ratings from teenagers with a mean of 4.70, while adults and experts both having a mean of 4.30 rated it *moderately acceptable*. This suggests that teenagers and experts find the visual appearance of the soap appealing, while adults have a slightly lower preference in terms of color.

In general, the Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts in Treatment 2 is *highly acceptable* to teenagers, receiving high ratings across all evaluation criteria as exhibited by a mean of 4.833. However, adults and experts find the soap to be *moderately acceptable*. The soap performs well in terms of hardness, cleansing, lathering, conditioning, fragrance, color, and the overall mean rating according to teenagers. Adults and experts, on the other hand, have slightly lower ratings in several aspects, particularly in lathering, fragrance, and conditioning. This indicates that the soap may not fully meet the preferences and expectations of adults and experts compared to teenagers.

Table 6. Degree of consumer's acceptability of calamansi Bath Soap Enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts in Three Treatments (Treatment 3)

Respondents						
Evaluation Criteria	Teenagers	Description	Adult	Description	Expert	Description
Hardness	4.90	Highly Acceptable	4.00	Moderately Acceptable	4.60	Highly Acceptable
Cleansing	4.70	Highly Acceptable	4.10	Moderately Acceptable	4.50	Highly Acceptable
Lathering	4.60	Highly Acceptable	3.70	Moderately Acceptable	4.00	Moderately Acceptable
Conditioning	4.90	Highly Acceptable	3.70	Moderately Acceptable	4.40	Moderately Acceptable
Fragrance	4.80	Highly Acceptable	3.40	Moderately Acceptable	4.20	Moderately Acceptable
Color	4.70	Highly Acceptable	3.50	Moderately Acceptable	4.50	Highly Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.767	Highly Acceptable	3.733	Moderately Acceptable	4.367	Moderately Acceptable

The data for Treatment 3 suggests that the degree of consumer acceptability of Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts varies among different groups. With these, for the respondents, the product using Treatment 3 is *moderately acceptable* with a grand mean of 4.289.

As to its hardness, the soap was *highly acceptable* to teenagers with a mean of 4.90, and experts with a mean of 4.60. However, adults rated it *moderately acceptable* with a mean of 4.00. This indicates that teenagers and experts find the soap's texture satisfactory, while adults have a slightly lower preference in terms of hardness.

In terms of the soap's cleansing ability, it received *highly acceptable* ratings from teenagers having a mean of 4.70, and experts having a mean of 4.50. However, adults with a mean of 4.10 perceived it as *moderately acceptable*. This suggests that the soap effectively cleans the skin according to the expectations of teenagers and experts, but adults have a slightly lower satisfaction level in this aspect.

With regard to the soap's lathering, teenagers rated the soap's lathering ability with a mean of 4.60 which is *highly acceptable*, while adults and experts rated it moderately acceptable. This implies that younger users generally prefer the soap's lathering, while adults and experts have a slightly lower preference in this regard.

In terms of conditioning, the soap's conditioning properties were *highly acceptable* to teenagers as substantiated by a mean of 4.90, moderately acceptable to experts, and *moderately acceptable* to adults as showed by the means of 3.70 and 4.40, respectively. This suggests that the soap provides satisfactory moisturization and softness to the skin according to teenagers, but experts and adults have a slightly lower satisfaction level in this aspect.

As to fragrance, with a mean of 4.80, the soap's fragrance received *highly acceptable* ratings from teenagers, but it was rated *moderately acceptable* as shown by the means of 3.40 and 4.20, respectively by adults and experts. This indicates that the scent of the soap is more appealing to teenagers compared to adults and experts.

In terms of color, with a mean of 4.70, the soap's color received *highly acceptable* ratings from teenagers and experts with a mean of 4.50, but it was rated *moderately acceptable* by adults as shown by a mean of 3.50. This suggests that teenagers and experts find the visual appearance of the soap appealing, while adults have a slightly lower preference in terms of color.

Overall, the Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts in Treatment 3 is *highly acceptable* to teenagers, with high ratings across most evaluation criteria. However, adults and experts have lower ratings, indicating a *moderate level of acceptability* for these groups. The soap performs well in terms of hardness, cleansing, fragrance, and color according to teenagers. However, adults and experts have slightly lower ratings in several aspects, including hardness, cleansing, lathering, conditioning, fragrance, color, and the overall mean rating. This suggests that the soap may not fully meet the preferences and expectations of adults and experts compared to teenagers.

General Level of Acceptability of the Three Treatments of Calamansi Bath Soap Enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts as Perceived by Respondents

Table 7. Comparison in the general level of acceptability of the three treatments of calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extracts as perceived by the respondents

Treatment	F-Value	p-Value	Decision	Remarks
Treatment 1	2.3722	0.1273	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Treatment 2	17.8606	0.0001	Reject H_0	Significant
Treatment 3	34.9084	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant

The table displays the comparison between Treatment 1 and the other treatments. Based on the data, it was found that there is no significant difference in the general level of acceptability. The p-value is greater than the significance level (usually 0.05), indicating that the difference is not statistically significant. In addition, the comparison between Treatment 2 and the other treatments shows that there is a significant difference in the general level of acceptability. The p-value is less than the significance level, indicating that the difference is statistically significant. Also, the comparison between Treatment 3 and the other treatments shows that there is a significant difference in the general level of acceptability. The p-value is less than the significance level, indicating that the difference is statistically significant.

The analysis shows that there is no significant difference in the general level of acceptability between Treatment 1 and the other treatments. This means that Treatment 1, which may represent the control or standard formulation of the soap, is perceived to have a similar level of acceptability as the other treatments.

Also, the analysis reveals a significant difference in the general level of acceptability between Treatment 2 and the other treatments. The lower p-value (less than the significance level) indicates that Treatment 2 has a distinct impact on the overall acceptability of the soap compared to Treatment 1 and Treatment 3. This suggests that Treatment 2, which likely involves specific enhancements or modifications to the soap, results in significantly different consumer perceptions and acceptability.

Similar to Treatment 2, the analysis demonstrates a significant difference in the general level of acceptability between Treatment 3 and the other treatments. The very low p-value indicates that Treatment 3 has a substantial impact on the overall acceptability of the soap compared to both Treatment 1 and Treatment 2. Treatment 3

likely introduces unique enhancements or changes that significantly affect how consumers perceive and accept the product.

Overall, the statistical analysis indicates that there is no significant difference in the general level of acceptability between Treatment 1 and the other treatments. However, there are significant differences in the general level of acceptability between Treatment 2 and Treatment 1, as well as between Treatment 3 and Treatment 1. This suggests that Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 have an impact on the overall acceptability of the Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts, while Treatment 1 does not significantly differ from the others. These findings suggest that specific modifications made in Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 result in distinct consumer perceptions and preferences, making them stand out from the control treatment (Treatment 1). Further investigation or analysis would be beneficial to identify the specific aspects or enhancements in Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 that contribute to their significant differences in acceptability.

Antibacterial Analysis of the Calamansi Bath Soap Enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts

The antibacterial analysis of Blue-Mansi soap is presented in Table 5. The data was obtained from reports analysis made by the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) Regional Office No.2 based in Tuguegarao City, Cagayan.

Table 8. Antimicrobial analysis of the calamansi bath soap enhanced with blue ternate flower extracts

Sample Code	Sample Description	ZONE INHIBITION (mm)	
		STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS	ESCHERICHIA COLI
MIC-0645	Blue Ternate soap	10	7
NEGATIVE CONTROL: Distilled Water		6	6

Based on the report analysis, the test/calibration requested by the researcher is the antimicrobial susceptibility test with the following test methods namely; Staphylococcus Aureus and Escherichia Coli. According to the report analysis, the Blue Ternate soap is partially active in terms of Staphylococcus Aureus at 10 mm while Escherichia Coli is inactive at 7mm. This means that the Blue-Mansi soap is safe to use in terms of staphylococcus while it is inactive in *E.Coli*.

Conclusions

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts, across various treatments, shows strong potential for development and commercial production. The soap was generally well-received by evaluators across different age groups, exhibiting high levels of acceptability in critical aspects such as hardness, cleansing, lathering, conditioning, fragrance, and color. Treatment 1, in particular, stood out with the highest ratings, indicating its suitability for a broad consumer base. Additionally, the soap was confirmed to be safe for human use, as it showed no significant microbial presence, including *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. These findings underscore the product's viability in the market and its potential to meet consumer needs effectively while ensuring safety.

Recommendations

In light of the aforementioned conclusions, the study recommends the following:

1. Capitalize on the positive reception of the Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts in Treatment 1. Focus on maintaining high acceptability in terms of hardness, cleansing, conditioning, color, and overall mean rating. Consider conducting further research and development to optimize the soap's lathering and fragrance, taking into account the slight variation in preferences among different groups.
2. Recognize the variation in preferences among different target consumer groups. Tailor marketing strategies to highlight the aspects that resonate most with each group. For teenagers, emphasize the soap's lathering ability and fragrance, as they showed higher satisfaction in these areas. For adults and experts, emphasize the soap's overall effectiveness, conditioning properties, and natural ingredients.
3. Develop informative materials that communicate the unique benefits of the Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts to the target consumer groups. Highlight the natural ingredients, their skincare benefits, and the soap's ability to cleanse and condition the skin effectively. Address any concerns or questions consumers may have about the soap's lathering or fragrance to build trust and increase adoption.
4. Design packaging that appeals to the target consumer groups while communicating the soap's key attributes and benefits. Consider incorporating elements that convey a fresh and appealing scent for the teenage group. For adults and experts, emphasize the soap's natural and high-quality ingredients. Leverage the positive aspects highlighted in the findings, such as hardness, cleansing, conditioning, and color, in the packaging and branding materials.
5. Conduct additional investigation or analysis to identify the specific aspects or enhancements in Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 that contribute to their significant

differences in acceptability. This could involve conducting surveys, focus groups, or interviews to gather qualitative feedback from consumers. Understanding the specific modifications that made Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 stand out from Treatment 1 will provide valuable insights for product refinement and future development.

6. Based on the findings, consider incorporating the modifications or enhancements present in Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 into the overall formulation of the Calamansi Bath Soap enhanced with Blue Ternate Flower Extracts. This could help improve the overall acceptability of the soap and meet the preferences of the target consumer groups.
7. Leverage the significant differences in acceptability between Treatment 2 and Treatment 1, as well as between Treatment 3 and Treatment 1, in your marketing strategy. Highlight the specific aspects or enhancements that differentiate Treatment 2 and Treatment 3, emphasizing how they contribute to an enhanced user experience. Use this information to position Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 as unique and superior options compared to Treatment 1.
8. Based on the significant differences in acceptability between treatments, consider segmenting the target consumer groups to align with their preferences. Tailor marketing messages and product positioning to each segment, highlighting the treatment option that aligns with their preferences and expectations. This will allow you to better address the diverse needs and preferences of different consumer groups.
9. Keep track of consumer feedback and market trends to ensure ongoing product improvement and innovation. Regularly assess consumer perceptions and preferences through surveys, reviews, and other feedback channels. This will help you stay responsive to changing consumer demands and maintain a competitive edge in the market.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher adhered to ethical standards throughout the study, maintaining integrity, transparency, and respect for the participants' rights. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before the study, with measures in place to protect their well-being. There were no conflicts of interest, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. The findings were interpreted without bias, and the results were used exclusively for the study.

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